

METHODS OF USING WAYS OF SAYING "SUVOVA" MUSIC PERFORMANCE OF KHORAZM IN YOUTH EDUCATION

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Annotation: In this article, one of the most important problems today is the theoretical basis of the method of using Khorezm murals to direct the upbringing of the mature generation in a positive direction.

Key words: Music culture, art, education and upbringing, Suvora, methodology, educational tools.

Holidays and the traditions, customs and ceremonies that are part of them are of great importance in the formation of a perfect personality. Holidays have national, spiritual, socio-political and cultural-educational significance, and the art of music stands out. Music festivals celebrated in Uzbekistan, the essence of the musical and artistic events held as an important factor in the development of youth education. Because of this, newly held holidays, pageants, festivals, and entertainment events of our youth are included in them, and features related to the rules of etiquette are embodied in them.

Through the events, young people see their own reflections and draw conclusions. However, the implementation of the above ideas in the preparation of such events will definitely depend on their organizations. At this point, I would like to emphasize that not all of our young people know how to respect such events. I mean, to be honest, they're not even interested in the event. At such times, it is necessary for the organizers to get active and organize popular and interesting events.

The mural sayings, which are the foundation of the music art of Khorezm, which we are discussing, have always been interesting for young people. This alone makes it easier to organize an event. Based on this, it is possible to organize interesting contests, shows and intellectual games. No matter what event we hold, the main idea of its content should be our ancient customs, traditions, rich historical heritage left by our ancestors. In these holidays, the art of music is definitely addressed. Because holidays and events will not be interesting without musicologists and singers.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" also correctly indicates the necessity of pedagogues to perform such honorable tasks, given ample room for their organizational skills.

In general, the main tasks of every pedagogue working in secondary schools or in various artistic activities are to provide knowledge to students during the lesson, and at the same time to organize musical and goal-oriented educational activities in the classroom or outside the school. . The main goal of events held in educational institutions and their organizers, pedagogues (music teachers), is to organize a well-rounded generation with a deep understanding of our national values.

Students' attention to national classical music art, young people are morally formed in the course of rich events using their national musical traditions. The solemn celebration of many events as a big public holiday at the state level and our great ancestors Ahmad Yassavi, Imam al-Bukhari, Hakim at-Tirmizi world science and great leaders of national Uzbek statehood Al-Khorazmi, Ahmad Fargani, Celebrating the jubilee celebrations of Mirzo Ulug'bek, Amir Temur and Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Komilojon Otaniyozov, Ortiq Otajhonov is a tribute to our independence.

Traditions are the best life lessons in human life since ancient times. It would not be wrong to call them guidance lessons for their generations. Music education plays a special role in helping young people find their place in the community they stay with during their time spent in general secondary schools or in various traditional singing clubs. Musical events based on specific content, school, extracurricular activities and general musical environment serve as an important resource for the formation of the students' spirituality.

The President of our country and the leaders of the Government attach great importance to the cultural education of children. The proof of this is that schoolchildren can enter theaters, concert halls, and philharmonics once a month. This decision set a big task for the employees of public education and the employees of cultural institutions. In general education schools, secondary special vocational educational institutions and higher educational institutions, one day every month is announced as "Spiritual Day" and teachers come to the educational institution in the prescribed manner. it is necessary to prepare to go to theaters, spiritual and educational places.

It is necessary for cultural institutions to take into account the uniqueness of young students and find suitable forms of performances and performances. For this, you should try to complete the following tasks.

- development of themes of useful cultural events based on the directions of musical and artistic education;

- creating thematic concert programs on suvora performance. In this, it is necessary to take into account the age characteristics of students and the characteristics of musical literacy of each group;
- development of full interviews and explanations given before the performance;
- in the program of a thematic concert intended for students, it is necessary to pay attention to its content being different. The sameness bores the students. The thematic concert is colorful, and most importantly, works dedicated to the classical music of Khorezm must have a mix of suvora expressions;

Then the students will compare the performed suvoras and the skills of the performers. Their perception of artistic analysis of music is activated.

As a conclusion, it is worth noting that Khorezm Suvora, which is an integral foundation of national music, educates students and introduces them to the world of music. serves to develop taste, feel beauty, and develop musical learning.

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